

A comparative study of orientation at behavior of univalent in living grasshopper spermatocytes

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Abstract

Oriental movements and modes of segregation at anaphase I were analyzed in three different types of univalents in living spermatocytes of the grass hopper species *Eyprepocnemis plorans*, namely the sex univalent, three types of accessory chromosomes and spontaneous and induced autosomal univalents. When two or more univalents were present in the same spindle, their dynamics were directly compared. Chromosomes may show variable velocity and number of reorientations: the X and the most common B types (B1 and B2) are slow and rarely reorient, a more geographically restricted B (B5) is faster and reorients more often, and autosomal univalents are the fastest and show the highest frequency of reorientations. Nonetheless, the X and the accessories are rigorously reductional at anaphase I whereas autosomal univalents often fail to migrate or divide equationally. This indicates that orientational and segregational behavior are controlled mainly by chromosomal rather than cellular characteristics and that chromosomes may display a great variety of strategies to achieve regular segregation.

Introduction

Unpaired chromosomes, univalents, are a source of irregularity in meiosis. Unlike bivalents, univalents cannot be stabilized by tension forces since they lack a partner attached to the opposite spindle pole. Univalents usually undergo a series of orientational and reorientational movements (Ostergren 1951; Dietz 1956; Nicklas 1961) that may end in reductional segregation to one pole or equational separation of chromatids at anaphase I through amphitelic chromosomal orientation. Amphitelic orientations are bipolar and stable but usually cause chromosomal lagging (Bauer et al. 1961), hence the risk of not reaching the poles at the first meiotic division and, even if chromatids succeed in being included in the daughter nuclei, they often lag and are lost in the second anaphase. There are, however, many examples of chromosomes— mostly sex chromosomes— that, despite their univalent condition, have managed to achieve regular transmission in meiosis, sometimes through sophisticated strategies, including nonrandom distance-segregation (see Wolf 1994 for review). In grasshopper species with sex determinism XX-XO, such mechanisms have not been reported; however, the sex univalent in male meiosis is rigorously reductional in anaphase I and equational in anaphase II, indicating the existence of a control preventing incorrect segregations. In some species of grasshoppers, chromosomes other than the X may naturally appear as univalents in the first division spindle; these are B chromosomes. The species *Eyprepocnemis plorans* possesses complex polymorphism for accessory chromosomes, where many different types have been described (Henriques-Gil et al. 1982, 1984b). The most common and widespread B variants display very regular meiotic behavior similar to the X: syntelic orientation followed by reductional segregation in the first meiotic division and amphitelic orientation followed by equational segregation in the second division. In contrast, amphitelic orientations at metaphase I are frequent in rare B variants with a high rate of chromosomal loss at either division.

Spontaneous autosomal univalents are rarely found since genetic control of crossover distribution ensures bivalent formation in all chromosomal pairs (alternative mechanisms for bivalent maintenance are equally efficient in achiasmatic meioses). Nevertheless, it is possible to induce univalency by altering

the meiotic stages in which pairing and crossing over occur. High temperature, for instance, is an easy treatment that proved to be effective in reducing chiasma formation and producing univalents in the locust *Schistocerca gregaria* (Henderson 1963).

Although the meiotic behavior of univalents can be readily analyzed in fixed material, and their rate of transmission can be deduced from the offspring of directed crosses as well, it is clear that chromosomal dynamics can only be addressed in living cells. It is possible that the same final outcome is the result of very different chromosomal strategies as occurs in two related species of the genus *Melanoplus* (Ault 1986), where the X is flawlessly reductional in anaphase I; in *Melanoplus san guinipes* the X is a static chromosome anchored to the spindle, whereas in *Melanoplus differentialis* it is very dynamic, moving between the poles throughout pro metaphase. In this study, the grasshopper species *E. plorans* was used as it is a good system for in vivo analysis of the orientational behavior of univalents because, in addition to the X, many individuals carry accessory chromosomes of different types. Moreover, autosomal univalents could be obtained by heat treatment at early meiotic stages (a pair of spontaneous autosomal univalents was also found). As two or more different kinds of univalents may be present within the same spindle, their orientational behavior can be directly compared. This allows us to analyze to what extent orientational strategies are controlled by chromosomal, rather than cellular characteristics.

Materials and methods

Individuals from three natural Spanish populations of *E. plorans* in which the predominant B types are different in size, structure, and C-banding pattern were chosen (see Henriques-Gil et al. 1984b):

Daimuz (DA) with B1 as the predominant type, representative of the Eastern populations

Benajarafe (BJ) with B2, representative of the central area of the distribution of the species

Fuengirola (FG) with B5, representative of a small, distinct locality at the border of the central and western areas of the distribution

All these B chromosomes are partially homologous since they can form chiasmata with one another when two different Bs are present in the same individual (Henriques-Gil et al. 1984a). B1 is considered the original type in the Iberian Peninsula from which all the other variants derived, establishing, in a relatively short period of time, a complex polymorphism where more than 30 different accessory chromosomes have been found (Henriques-Gil et al. 1984b; Henriques-Gil and Arana 1990).

The three samples were maintained in the laboratory at a constant 30° C and with a 12-h photoperiod.

To characterize the in vivo behavior of the X chromosome alone, individuals without Bs from Daimuz were analyzed. For the study of B and autosomal univalents, individuals with only one B and a pair of medium-sized autosomal univalents were selected, respectively; the behavior of the X chromosome was also analyzed in these cells (see Table 1).

Autosomal univalents were induced by heat treatment of young adult males at 44° C for 4 days. Prometaphase I univalents could be observed after 2 days of recovery in normal laboratory conditions. One pair of spontaneous univalents was also analyzed.

The chromosomal constitution of the grasshoppers was checked by testicular biopsy. Some follicles were fixed in 1:3 acetic acid:ethanol and C-banded to identify chromosomes, and the rest were used for in vivo analysis following the culture method of Nicklas et al. (1982).

Living spermatocytes were tracked from the earliest prometaphase I stage found in the culture until anaphase I (the average duration of the whole prometaphase in the cultures being about 5.5 h). A series of photographs at different focal levels to show the centrioles and centromeric regions of all univalents was taken at approximately 15 min intervals and also whenever a reorientational movement occurred.

The cells were reconstructed from images projected at 2600x using a photographic enlarger. To estimate the distance covered by each chromosome in an interval, the midpoints of the cellular axes in two consecutive series were superimposed and the straight distance between the centromeric positions of each chromosome was measured; velocities were then calculated for each interval. As in each culture, prometaphase cells could be at a different stage and the duration of prometaphase itself is variable between cells, the number of velocity estimates is different in each case.

Results

Morphology and behavior of univalents

All univalents move between poles and are capable of reorientation at any time in prometaphase. They may also show lateral displacements or stay still, and their position can be either central or peripheral within the spindle. However, each chromosome has some specific characteristics concerning in vivo morphology and dynamic behavior.

Figure 1 shows schematic drawings of the typical trajectories described by different chromosomes during prometaphase. Each straight segment represents the distance covered by a chromosome in a 15-min interval; the junctions between two consecutive straight lines are thus the successive positions of the chromosomes when the corresponding series of photographs was taken. As is obvious from Fig. 1, the various chromosomal types behave in different ways: the X and B₁ (and B₂ as well, though not included in the figure) show little net displacement (short straight segments in the figure) and as a consequence, they do not display much variation in their positions in the spindle during prometaphase. In fact, these chromosomes may spend the whole prometaphase traveling from the equator to the pole (see Fig. 1). On the contrary, B₅ and autosomal univalents perform long sustained polar movements (long straight segments in the figure), hence they may occupy a greater diversity of positions in the prometaphase spindle. This behavior is linked to a high frequency of reorientations. We consider these chromosomes to be more dynamic. In order to compare the behavior of different univalents within the same spindle, we characterize chromosomal dynamics in terms of net displacements - through velocity estimates - and frequency of reorientations.

The main characteristics of the in vivo morphology and dynamic behavior of each chromosomal type are as follows:

Chromosome X (Fig. 2) is faint and somewhat deconstructed in phase contrast. Two small dots or a thin darker band can be distinguished at the centromeric end. Poleward movements are slow and interrupted by static periods where only small oscillations may occur. This chromosome rarely reorients (11 out of 37 chromosomes reoriented once; the remainder did not reorient at all) or covers the entire interpolar distance. It is syntelic throughout prometaphase (except for the transient amphitelic orientations that may occur during reorientation) and anaphase I is always reductional.

Chromosome B₁ (Fig. 2) is also faint but approximately half the size of the X. The centromeric end often shows a pair of dark dots or a thin dark band. It moves slowly and rarely reorients (five out of nine chromosomes reoriented once). It is syntelic at prometaphase and anaphase I is generally reductional (equational divisions were never seen in vivo but in previous studies of fixed cells it has been estimated to be about 4%; Henriques-Gil et al. 1982).

Chromosome B₂ (Fig. 3) is similar to B₁ in appearance and behavior but clearly smaller. In one cell out of nine, B₂ reoriented twice, in two cells it reoriented once and it did not reorient in the remaining cells. Like B₁, it shows a 4% rate of equational divisions.

Chromosome B₅ (Fig. 4) resembles B₁ in size and appearance but it is much more dynamic: it moves faster, may realize complete interpolar trips, and reorients more often, with a maximum of five

reorientations per cell and a minimum of one. Amphitelic orientations are frequent - four out of nine chromosomes - but in the cells analyzed here, undivided laggards always end up included in one of the anaphase I poles (Fig. 5). Its frequency of equational division estimated in fixed secondary spermatozoa is also close to 4%.

Autosomal univalents (Fig. 6) are darker than the X and Bs in phase contrast. Centromeric ends are not evident morphologically, and they are assumed to be at the leading end of chromosomal movements. As only medium-sized chromosomes were chosen, they are similar to B₁ and B₅. The two homologs within a spindle move independently of each other. They are very dynamic: they move faster and reorient more often (with a maximum of eight and a minimum of one reorientation per cell, see Table 4) than the other univalent types and show frequent complete or incomplete interpolar trips. They usually remain active until the onset of anaphase but sometimes stabilize at the equator by the end of prometaphase, decreasing their speed and attaining the amphitelic orientation that produces anaphase lagging - four out of ten chromosomes analyzed behaved thus. Segregation in anaphase may be reductional or equational. Only one equational segregation was scored in the cells analyzed here, but it has been observed in other living spermatocytes (unpublished data). Actually, the rate of disjunction abnormalities in laggards - including migration failure and equational division - is higher than 50% (Figs. 7 and 8).

Velocities

Minimum, maximum, and mean velocities were calculated for each chromosome in each cell (taking into account all the velocity estimates). When the parameters are averaged for each chromosomal type (Table 1), it can be seen that all univalents present similar minimum velocities, but the mean and maximum velocities of B₅ and autosomal univalents are higher. This reflects the fact that the last two types may stay still for a time like the other chromosomes, but when they move, they do it faster. Taking maximum velocities as a good estimation of the dynamic capability of a chromosome, they were scored for each chromosome in each cell, and then the resulting nine chromosomal categories (listed in Table 1) were compared by a Kruskal-Wallis test that showed significant differences ($H=35.49$, $\chi^2=35.54$, 8 df, $P<0.005$). When Wilcoxon's two-samples tests were performed, only B₅ and the autosomal univalents showed significant differences from each other and with the remaining chromosomes. The maximum velocity for B₅ is higher than that of X, B₁, or B₂ but lower than that of autosomal univalents. Maximum velocities do not reveal aspects of chromosome behavior such as the relative importance of static and dynamic periods, continuity or discontinuity of interpolar motions, and duration of reorientations. To analyze these aspects of behavior, all the estimates of velocity (per 15 min interval) for each chromosome were compared, pooling the data of the cells with the same chromosomal constitution. The Kruskal-Wallis test for the nine chromosomal categories was significant ($H= 177.22$, $\chi^2=177.23$, 8 df, $P<0.005$). The results of Wilcoxon's two-samples tests are shown in Table 2. Heterogeneity is observed between X chromosomes from different populations: X from FG [X (B5)] is slower than Xs from DA [X (OB), X (B1), and X (A)]; B1 and B2 behave alike and are in general similar to the X chromosomes [except for X (B5) which is slower], B5 is faster than the Xs, B1, and B2 but slower than autosomal univalents (A), and these are clearly faster than any other univalent type. When Bs or autosomal univalents were compared with the Xs within the same cell by a sign test for paired observations (faster univalent in each 15 min interval), only B5 and As were significantly faster than their respective Xs, supporting the results obtained in the Wilcoxon's tests.

The fact that the X chromosome from the FG population [X (BS)] is slower than the Xs from the DA population [X (OB), X (B1), and X (A)], could be the result of a cellular effect that decreases the velocity of all the univalents within the same spindle; thus B5 would actually appear slower than it might be in a different cellular environment. To check whether velocity differences between B₅ and autosomal

univalents are at least in part due to intrinsic chromosomal characteristics, all the velocity values obtained for B_5 were increased by an amount proportional to the difference between the mean velocities of their respective X chromosomes [$X(BS)$ and $X(A)$]. Wilcoxon's two-samples test shows that B_5 is still significantly slower than autosomal univalents ($Z=4.71$, $P<0.001$). Up to this point the results indicate that, in velocity and frequency of reorientations, the B_5 chromosome is intermediate between X, B_1 , and B_2 on the one hand, and autosomal univalents on the other.

Prometaphase progression

To check whether dynamic chromosomal characteristics are constant throughout prometaphase and to discard possible misleading effects due to differences in the duration of the cells, prometaphase tracks, the data for each cell were arbitrarily divided into 1 h intervals, starting at the onset of anaphase and proceeding backward to early pro metaphase. Both velocities and numbers of reorientations were classified into hours before anaphase. All the data for each chromosomal type were pooled regardless of the cell of origin. Again, due to the variable duration of the tracks, the number of velocity estimates is different for each hourly interval; early prometaphase stages are obviously less well represented than late stages. Raw velocity data were used in the statistical tests.

A global Kruskal-Wallis test including all the velocity estimates for all chromosome types grouped into hours before anaphase as described above showed significant differences ($H=210.49$, $\chi^2=210.64$, 27 df, $P<0.005$). When the same tests were used to compare the velocities of a given chromosome throughout prometaphase, only B_5 and autosomal univalents showed significant variations in velocity (for B_5 , $H=20.99$, $\chi^2=21.6$, 6 df, $P<0.005$; for autosomal univalents, $H=14.19$, $\chi^2=14.19$, 3 df, $P<0.005$). When velocity estimates within each hour are averaged and plotted (Fig. 9) it appears that B_5 and autosomal univalents reach maximum velocities at the second and third hours before anaphase, respectively. Wilcoxon's two-samples tests comparing the hourly intervals two by two confirm this observation (for B_5 , the peak of velocity at the second hour differs from the velocities of the first, fourth and fifth, and the third also differs from the fifth; for autosomal univalents the peak at the third hour is different from the velocities of the first and the second hours). It is remarkable that by the end of prometaphase, both B_5 and autosomes may adopt amphitelic orientations, and then assume relatively stable positions near the equator and cease making interpo lar trips. This happened for four out of nine B_5 chromosomes and for four out of ten autosomes. In the remaining cases, the B_5 and autosomal univalents do not reduce their activity until the onset of anaphase. Hence, the decrease in velocity at the end of prometaphase shown by these chromosomes (see Fig. 9) is mostly due to amphitelic stabilization.

Finally, all chromosomes were compared with one another by Wilcoxon's tests and the results, shown in Table 3, indicate that B_5 behaves like the X, B_1 , and B_2 chromosomes at early prometaphase but from the third hour before anaphase on, it speeds up, resembling the As at the late stages. Autosomal univalents in turn are clearly faster than X, B_1 , and B_2 throughout prometaphase but they only differ from B_5 in the earliest stages analyzed (fourth and third hours before anaphase).

When reorientations are scored according to hours before anaphase (Table 4), it appears that both B_5 and autosomal univalents show a maximum at the third hour before anaphase, which, for the latter, coincides with their maximum velocity (see Fig. 9).

Discussion

Like the X chromosome of the grasshopper *M. differentialis* studied in vivo by Nicklas (1961), all the univalent types analyzed in *E. plorans* are unstable in orientation: they are capable of reorienting and making an interpo lar trip at any time throughout prometaphase (Table 4). Hence these chromosomes lack

any specific anchoring or stabilizing mechanism such as that described by Ault (1984) for the X of *M. sanguinipes*. It is remarkable that B₅ and autosomal univalents are the chromosomes of *E. plorans* most resembling the X of *M. differentialis* in terms of velocity and number of reorientations - with a mean velocity of 0.73 µm/min in complete interpolar trips, compared with 0.66 µm/min for *E. plorans* autosomal univalents and 0.50 µm/min for B₅ in the same movements, whereas the X chromosome of *E. plorans* is far less dynamic - only two long trips covering at least half the spindle were scored for this chromosome, and their velocities were 0.20 µm/min and 0.12 µm/min, respectively. The behavior of B₅ and autosomal univalents differs however from the X of *M. differentialis* in the possibility of amphitelic orientations, which never occur in the sex univalents of both species.

Dynamic behavior in relation to chromosomal nature

Sharon and Simchen (1990) demonstrated beautifully in yeast meiotic mutants that the choice between reductional or equational segregation of chromosomes at meiosis depends mostly on chromosomal - specifically centromeric - characteristics (see also Simchen and Hugerat 1993, for review). The importance of specific chromosomal characteristics in meiotic behavior is also revealed in this study, regarding not only anaphase I segregation but also prometaphase dynamics.

A single example of differential prometaphase movements was described by Ault (1984) in one cell of *M. sanguinipes* with two spontaneous autosomal univalents, although, as mentioned before, in this species the X has a specific anchoring mechanism through microtubules impinging on its decondensed chromatin that none of the *E. plorans* univalent types studied here seem to have evolved since of all of them may reorient at any time in prometaphase. In *E. plorans*, the differential behavior of each univalent type correlates with its nature; the X chromosome is always a univalent in primary spermatocytes of many grasshopper species, which have XX-XO sexual determinism, and its meiotic regularity is essential for the correct segregation of sex chromosomes to the gametes. This implies that it must have been subject to selective pressure regulating its meiotic behavior. B chromosomes on the contrary are not essential for survival and there is no evidence in *E. plorans* that they bring selective advantage to the bearers, thus maintenance of polymorphism in natural populations would depend on intragenomic selection acting on the effectiveness of their mechanisms of transmission (see Henriques-Gil and Arana 1990; Lopez Leon et al. 1992). Though they never pair with chromosomes of the normal complement, they do not always appear as univalents but may form bivalents and even multivalents when there are more than one in the same individual. Autosomes, except for rare meiotic errors, always form bivalents in the first meiotic division so it is unlikely that their behavior as univalents has been modeled by any kind of selection whether natural or intragenomic. Moreover, the deleterious consequences of autosomal univalency not only result from the risk of equational divisions at anaphase I but also from the independent reductional segregation of homologs that will give rise to 50% unbalanced gametes. This is obviously irrelevant in the case of accessory chromosomes.

The transmission of B₁ and B₂ is almost as regular as

that of the X chromosome and this quality seems to have been achieved by using the same dynamic strategy as the sex univalent; transmission of B₅ is equally efficient although it involves a somewhat more "risky" strategy as anaphase laggards are produced that, nonetheless, end up segregating correctly, and autosomal univalents are the most irregular in dynamics and segregation.

From the geographical distribution of accessories in natural populations of *E. plorans* in the Iberian Peninsula, B₁ appears to be the original and most widespread type, and the other variants to have been derived from it by chromosomal mutation (Henriques-Gil et al. 1984b), B₂ is an ancient and well-represented derivative, and B₅ is a common type but restricted to a very small geographic area.

Besides the already mentioned reductional segregation of B₅ anaphase I laggards, its relative irregularity in vivo can also be mitigated by the fact that the frequency of accessories in the area spanned by B₅ is so high that many individuals bear more than one B chromosome, thus these have a good chance of forming bivalents and multivalents.

Factors affecting dynamic chromosomal behavior

Due to the variable duration of the cells' prometaphase tracks analyzed, any cellular effect on prometaphase progression like a gradual decrease in spindle activity (Nicklas 1961; Ostergren et al. 1960) could produce artificial differences between chromosomes. However, such an effect is not obvious in *E. plorans* since when hourly intervals are compared, neither the X, nor B₁ and B₂ show any decrease in velocity or number of reorientations at late prometaphase (see Fig. 9), and the overall reduction seen in B₅ and autosomal univalents is due, rather, to the amphitelic stabilization of some of these chromosomes in a manner similar to that described by Arana and Nicklas (1992) for the long arms of *M. sangui nipes* quadrivalents. Also, the comparisons between chromosomes at the same prometaphase stage clearly indicate that the differences are real.

Among the various chromosomal characteristics that could account for the differential behavior of the univalents studied, size and degree of condensation can be ruled out. Thus, B₅ is as decondensed as the X, yet resembles in behavior the condensed autosomes, and B₁ and B₂ behave like the X, which is twice as big. Centromeric regions are the most important for chromosomal orientation and segregation. Kinetochores mediate the interactions of the chromosome with the spindle and are also the site for the "motors" determining movement (for review see Rieder 1991; McIntosh and Pfarr 1991), while centromeric chromatin plays an important role in determining syntelic segregation in the first meiotic division (reviewed by Miyazaki and Orr-Weaver 1994). So, most likely, the differences found in the behavior of univalents arise from differences at the level of the kinetochore and/or centromere and these will be discussed in more detail.

Degree of exposure of kinetochores

A crucial factor in prometaphase orientational and reorientational movements is the position of kinetochores. These preferentially attach to the pole they most directly face (Ostergren 1951; Nicklas 1967); however, they may capture microtubules from the other pole if they pass close enough and at an adequate interaction angle (Ault 1986). The degree of exposure to microtubules of a kinetochore may depend on its own structure, which will determine the amplitude of the interaction angle. The big protruding hemispherical kinetochores of *Drosophila melanogaster* facilitate the frequent reorientations of early prometaphase bivalents (Church and Lin 1985). Electron microscopic (EM) observations of *E. plorans* kinetochores reveal that they are not so exposed as those of *D. melanogaster* (Rufas et al. 1994). The tiny short arms present in the accessories but lacking in the remaining chromosomes of *E. plorans* do not seem to hinder reorientation through shielding of kinetochores as B₅ reorients more often than the telocentric X.

Doubleness of sister kinetochores

As prometaphase I proceeds, sister kinetochores gradually become distinguishably double structures (Goldstein 1981, Rufas et al. 1989, 1994) although they behave as a unit in the first meiotic division; increasing doubleness continues throughout meiosis allowing chromatid orientation and segregation at the second division.

Premature sister kinetochore separation is a source of abnormalities of disjunction (see Miyazaki and Orr

Weaver 1994 for review). Janicke and Lafountain (1989) treated *Nephrotoma suturalis* spermatocytes to prevent spindle formation. This did not stop kinetochore maturation, and consequently, when the cells recovered, the chromosomes had a higher degree of sister kinetochore doubleness when they began to interact with the spindle. This produced a high frequency of equational segregations at anaphase I. The same cause has been invoked to explain the amphitelic orientations found in *M. sanguinipes* quadrivalents that were repeatedly detached from the spindle by micromanipulation (Arana and Nicklas 1992). They also must begin the whole series of trial and error orientational movements at a later than normal time and hence with an initially higher degree of sister kinetochore separation.

In wheat univalents (Wagenaar and Bray 1973), sister kinetochore doubleness at the first meiotic division allows the attachment of only one chromatid kinetochore to the pole opposite to the one to which the chromosome was initially oriented. This new attachment provokes the rotation of the univalent and the subsequent reorientational movement toward the equatorial plate where it becomes amphitelic.

Hence, early separation of sister kinetochores could contribute to an increase in both the frequency of reorientations and final amphitelic orientations. In *E. plorans* the univalents that reorient more often (B_5 and autosomal univalents) are also the ones that may adopt amphitelic stabilization. This suggests that there may be differences between them in the velocity of kinetochore maturation. Asynchrony in the sequence of centromeric separation in mitosis has been reported in several species of plants and animals (see Vig and Paweletz 1988 for review) in relation to the amount, quality and timing of replication of pericentric heterochromatin: in general, chromosomes with no or small quantities of heterochromatin separate first. However, the presence of a large pericentromeric C-band in B_5 (Henriques-Gil et al. 1984b) does not prevent frequent reorientations or amphitelic stabilization but may hinder chromatid separation in anaphase laggards.

Kinetochore activity

In *E. plorans* velocity differences between univalents parallel their degree of orientational instability - the fastest chromosomes are also the most unstable - suggesting that all these chromosomal traits evolved together.

Factors like degree of exposure of kinetochores and sister kinetochore doubleness are more likely to affect the frequency of reorientations of a univalent rather than its velocity. However, a chromosome that rarely reorients, spending most of its time at or close to the pole, has few chances to demonstrate how fast it is capable of moving. Moreover, the highest velocities achieved by a chromosome often correspond to movements occurring immediately after a reorientation; if these are frequent, the mean velocity of the chromosome will be higher. Nevertheless, this relationship between reorientation and velocity cannot fully explain the differences in behavior between *E. plorans* univalents since the most static chromosomes, X, B_1 and B_2 , are also slow when they are moving as is evident from a comparison of maximum velocities (see Table 1). In addition, absolute maximum velocities of B_5 are lower in all but one out of nine cells than those of autosomal univalents even though B_5 reorients frequently, thus having many chances to reach a high speed.

It should be noted that velocity estimates are actually an average for a 15 min interval so the possibility that slow chromosomes can move at a high speed for short periods of time cannot be ruled out. However, it is evident that the net displacement of a chromosome during an interval, that is, the change in position within the spindle, is very different between univalents.

As reported by Skibbens et al. (1993), moving chromosomes may show velocity changes, pauses and switches between polar and antipolar movements, owing to what is referred to as kinetochore "directional instability". The pattern of movements of the X, B_1 and B_2 , with pauses, oscillations and

antipolar displacements without reorientation (see Fig. 1) agrees with a model of kinetochores with frequent phase switches. On the contrary, the kinetochores of B_5 and autosomal univalents might remain in the poleward movement phase for longer periods. The possibility that kinetochore motors are not equally efficient in all chromosomes cannot be ruled out, but a different type of experimental approach would be needed to test such an hypothesis.

It is worth mentioning that the behavior of the two spontaneous autosomal univalents is identical to that of heat-induced univalents so their instability is not due to chromosomal damage produced by the treatment. This is also supported by the normal behavior of the X chromosome in the same cells. Nevertheless, heat shock during the pairing phase of chromosomes may produce both asynapsis and desynapsis (Peacock 1968; Loidl 1989). This in turn, may alter the subsequent orientational behavior for instance, through an effect on sister chromatid cohesiveness. The lack of effect on the X is not relevant at this point as the sex chromosome does not pair in the males of XX-XO grasshopper species (Jones and Croft 1986; Santos et al. 1993).

The similarity in behavior of X, B_1 and B_2 could be taken as suggesting an evolutionary origin of accessories from the sex chromosome in *E. plorans*, however, the clearly distinct behavior of B_5 - a closely related accessory - makes it clear that dynamic features of a chromosome can change fast.

Finally, the variations found in the velocity of chromosome X in the DA and PG populations - the most geographically distant localities sampled - suggest that the genotype may also have an effect on overall chromosomal dynamics, but not so strongly, in this case, as to prevail on the variation due to intrinsic chromosomal characteristics.

That univalents may adopt very different strategies to assure regular transmission is obvious in the comparison of *Melanoplus* species (Ault 1986): *M. sanguinipes* has a static X whereas the X of *M. differentialis* is very fast (Nicklas 1961) and reorients frequently, yet it is flaw lessly reductional at the first anaphase.

The data analyzed here indicate that, in *E. plorans* regularity of transmission is related to low velocity and infrequent reorientations, since chromosomes of a very different nature like the X and the most common accessories, B_2 and B_2 , share the same characteristics. This however, does not imply that other chromosomes, even in the same species, have evolved different strategies that are equally efficient for regular transmission as is the case of B_5 .

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Figures

Fig. 1. Schematic drawings of typical trajectories described by different univalent types during prometaphase. Each straight segment represents one interval of approximately 15 min. Junctions between two consecutive segments are the successive positions of the chromosomes when they were measured. The X chromosome does not show any reorientation, B₁ reorients once (at the top of the drawing), B₅ reorients four times and the autosomal univalents reorient twice (*the one on the left*) and three times (*the one on the right*), respectively

Fig. 2. Prometaphase movements of the X (upper row) and B₁ (lower row) univalents in the same cell. Arrowheads mark the centromeric ends. The graph shows the position of chromosomes versus time; the upper and lower continuous lines represent the

position of spindle poles. The X and the accessory reorient once each (chromosome X, 190 min print; B₁, 223 min print). Both chromosomes are reductional at anaphase (325 min print). Bar represents 10 μm

Fig. 3. Prometaphase movements of B₂; there is no reorientation and anaphase I is reductional. *Arrowheads* mark the centromeric ends. Bar represents 10 μ m

Fig. 4. Prometaphase movements of B₅. Three reorientations are shown in the pictures (37, 144, and 253 min prints). The final orientation is amphitelic (308 min print), but segregation is always reductional (not shown). *Arrowheads* mark the centromeric ends. Bar represents 10 μ m

Fig. 5. B_5 amphitelic orientation (0 min print) producing anaphase I lagging of the chromosome (19 min print) which eventually segregates reductionally to the lower pole (31 and 54 min prints). *Arrowhead* marks the centromeric end. Bar represents 10 μm

Fig. 6. Prometaphase movements of one autosomal univalent with eight reorientations; only the second is shown in full in the pictures (10, 30, 58, 76, 116, 142, 168, and 194 min prints). Anaphase I is reductional (249 min print). *Arrowheads* mark the centromeric ends. Bar represents 10 μ m

Fig. 7. Telophase I sequence showing migrational failure of an autosomal laggard. Cytokinesis proceeds leaving the univalent (*arrow-heads*) in the cytoplasm of the upper daughter cell, and not included in the nuclear envelope. Bar represents 10 μm

Fig. 8. Equational anaphase I segregation of an autosomal univalent laggard. Centromeric ends separate first (*arrowheads*) (0 min print), leading the poleward movement (4 and 9 min prints). Bar represents 10 μm

Fig. 9. Average velocities per hour for each chromosomal type, classified into hours before anaphase I. Only B₅ and autosomal univalents show significant variations of velocity during prometaphase, reaching their maximum at the second and the third hours, respectively

Tables

Table 1. Analysis of velocities of univalents

Chromosome and population ^a	No. chromosomes	No. Individuals analyzed	Maximum velocity ^c (μm/min)	Minimum velocity ^c (μm/min)	Mean velocity ^c (μm/min)
X (OB) DA	5	3	0.38 (0.23–0.56)	0.05 (0.00–0.10)	0.16 (0.12–0.20)
X (B1) DA	9	3	0.30 (0.14–0.60)	0.03 (0.00–0.06)	0.13 (0.09–0.21)
X (B2) BJ	9 ^b	2	0.31 (0.11–0.60)	0.04 (0.00–0.09)	0.14 (0.08–0.28)
X (B5) FG	9	3	0.27 (0.19–0.45)	0.02 (0.00–0.05)	0.11 (0.09–0.17)
X (A) DA	5	3	0.27 (0.12–0.43)	0.05 (0.01–0.09)	0.13 (0.07–0.19)
B1 DA	9	3	0.40 (0.13–1.03)	0.04 (0.00–0.11)	0.16 (0.09–0.22)
B2 BJ	8	2	0.31 (0.08–0.53)	0.06 (0.00–0.14)	0.15 (0.09–0.21)
B5 FG	9	3	0.70 (0.31–1.25)	0.05 (0.00–0.10)	0.26 (0.12–0.43)
A DA	10	3	1.05 (0.37–1.43)	0.13 (0.04–0.38)	0.48 (0.17–0.74)

^a DA, Daimuz; BJ, Benjarafe; FG, Fuengirola

^b One cell with twoX chromosomes

^c Range of variation between cells in parentheses

Table 2. Wilcoxon's two-samples tests for comparisons of the velocities of the nine chromosomal categories considered, using all the 15 min velocity estimates

Chromosome and population	X (B1) DA	X (B2) DA	X (B5) FG	X (A) DA	B1 DA	B2 BJ	B5 FG	A DA
X (OB) DA	NS	NS	**	NS	NS	NS	*	***
X (B1) DA		NS	**	NS	NS	NS	***	***
X (B2) BJ			NS	NS	*	NS	***	***
X (B5) FG				**	***	**	***	***
X (A) DA					NS	NS	***	***
B1 DA						NS	**	***
B2 BJ							**	***
B5 FG								***

NS not significant; * $0.05 > P > 0.01$; ** $0.01 > P > 0.001$; *** $P < 0.001$

Table 3. Wilcoxon's two-samples tests for the comparison of chromosomal velocities during prometaphase

Chromosomes	Hours before anaphase					
	6	5	4	3	2	1
B1-X		*	NS	NS	*	NS
B2-X			NS	NS	NS	NS
B2-B1			NS	NS	NS	NS
B5-X	NS	NS	**	***	***	**
B5-B1		NS	NS	***	**	NS
B5-B2			NS	**	**	NS
A-X			***	***	***	***
A-B1			***	***	**	***
A-B2			*	***	***	***
A-B5			***	***	NS	NS

NS not significant; * $0.05 > P > 0.01$; ** $0.01 > P > 0.001$; *** $P < 0.001$
 All the X chromosomes are pooled

Table 4. Number of reorientations during prometaphase

Chromosome		Hours before anaphase							Total
		7	6	5	4	3	2	1	
X	No. chromosomes ^a	1	2	11	21	27	33	37	37
	No. reorientations	1	0	0	2	4	3	2	12
B1	No. chromosomes	–	–	–	6	7	8	9	9
	No. reorientations	–	–	–	0	1	2	2	5
B2	No. chromosomes	–	–	–	1	4	7	8	8
	No. reorientations	–	–	–	1	1	1	1	4
B5	No. chromosomes	1	2	5	9	9	9	9	9
	No. reorientations	0	0	1	4	10	8	2	25
A	No. chromosomes	–	–	–	6	8	8	10	10
	No. reorientations	–	–	–	7	15	7	9	38
Total	No. chromosomes	2	4	22	43	55	65	73	73
	No. reorientations	1	0	1	14	31	21	16	84

^a Note that the number of chromosomes scored increases as prometaphase proceeds, owing to the variable duration of the cell tracks